

**ADDRESSING PRESERVATION CHALLENGES IN NIGERIAN MUSEUMS
STRATEGIES FOR SAFEGUARDING CULTURAL HERITAGE**

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This study aimed to conceptualize and address preservation challenges in Nigerian museums; specifically exploring strategies for safeguarding cultural heritage that serves as both a functional center for community activities and a model for environmental responsibility. This study adopted a descriptive research design . The target population includes the community, comprising of residents, local organizations, and potential museum users. A purposive sampling technique was used to select a representative sample of stakeholders, including community leaders, educators, cultural practitioners, and environmental enthusiasts. The findings revealed that the key principles for sustainable museum design includes energy efficiency, water conservation, use of recycled materials, and minimizing the museum's carbon footprint. It was concluded that proposed plan incorporates sustainable design principles to minimize environmental impact while promoting social cohesion through its focus on community engagement. Hence the study recommends the need to conduct community consultations and workshops to refine the design based on local needs and preferences, and develop a detailed construction plan with cost estimates and identify potential funding sources among others.

Keywords: Museum, Preservation, Heritage, Cultural

Introduction

The role of museums and monuments in the socio-cultural development of society cannot be over emphasized. Recent studies indicate that the relevance of It is impossible to separate museums from the socio-cultural histories of world growth. Consequently, monuments and museums have developed into formal organizations tasked with passing down this legacy from one generation to the next. It is similarly important to note that museums have historical roots that extend beyond their physical buildings. Maintaining the cultural posterity of a people involves preserving additional content and collections inside a structure. Whether it's ancient artifacts or cutting-edge technology pieces, the museum continues to be the hub of living history. The official founding of museums began in Renaissance-era ancient Rome and expanded to other regions of Europe by the eighteenth century, the age of enlightenment. According to historical records, Rome founded the world's first public collection of artworks in 1471. Previously, it was called the Capitoline Museum.

The word "museum" and its concept gained popularity due to the operations of the Alexandrian Museum in 200 BC in Egypt, although its etymology can undoubtedly be traced back to the Greek and Roman centers for housing the goddesses of art and sciences.

This evolution has little to do with the advanced civilization that has historically characterized Africa, particularly Egypt. This development of museums persisted in Egypt, and by the 18th and 19th centuries, it had spread to other regions of the world. For instance, museums were founded in Ireland, France, America, and Britain in 1731, 1750, 1753, and 1759, respectively. Consequently, when colonialism spread widely, particularly in Africa, various organized Nigeria and Africa both saw the establishment of organized museums. In light of this, this study explores the evolution of museums in Nigeria throughout history, focusing on the National Museum located in Lagos.

A museum in Lagos holds significant cultural heritage importance, serving as a vital institution for preserving and showcasing the rich history, traditions, and artistic expressions of Nigeria and its diverse ethnic groups. Lagos, as a vibrant cultural hub, is home to various museums, such as

the National Museum Lagos, which houses an extensive collection of artifacts, including traditional art, historical relics, and archaeological treasures.

These museums play a crucial role in educating both locals and visitors about Nigeria's cultural history, fostering a sense of identity and continuity. They also serve as custodians of intangible cultural heritage, such as oral histories, traditional music, and customs, ensuring that these practices are documented and passed down to future generations. Furthermore, museums in Lagos contribute to cultural tourism, attracting international attention and promoting a deeper understanding of Nigeria's cultural diversity and historical legacy on a global scale.

Literature review

Different literatures related to the study were reviewed under the following subtitles

Concept of Cultural Heritage

Cultural heritage is the heritage of tangible and intangible heritage assets of a group or society that is inherited from past generations. Not all heritages of past generations are "heritage"; rather, heritage is a product of selection by society (Logan, William S, 2017). Cultural heritage includes tangible culture (such as buildings, monuments, landscapes, archive materials, books, works of art, and artifacts), intangible culture (such as folklore, traditions, language, and knowledge), and natural heritage (including culturally significant landscapes, and biodiversity) (Ann Marie Sullivan, 2016).

Architectural designs and cultural heritage

Architectural design and cultural heritage are intricately intertwined, forming a dynamic relationship where each shapes and influences the other. Buildings serve not just as functional structures, but as physical manifestations of a culture's values, traditions, and history. On one hand, cultural heritage serves as a wellspring of inspiration for architects. Traditional building materials, techniques, and aesthetics often find themselves reinterpreted and integrated into contemporary designs. This is evident in the works of architects like Glenn Murcutt, whose

Australian projects seamlessly blend indigenous knowledge of the land with modern design principles (s3da-design, 2023)

Concept of museums

A museum is an institution dedicated to displaying and/or preserving culturally significant objects. Many museums have exhibitions of these objects on public display, and some have private collections that are used by researchers and specialists. Compared to a library, a museum hosts a much wider range of objects and usually focus around a specific theme such as the arts, science, natural history, local history, and other topics (Findlen, Paula, 1989). Public museums that host exhibitions and interactive demonstrations are often considered to be tourist attractions, and many museums attract large numbers of visitors from outside their host country, with the most visited museums in the world regularly attracting millions of visitors annually. Since the establishment of the earliest known museum in ancient times, museums have been associated with academia and the preservation of rare items. Museums originated as private collections of interesting items, and only much later did the emphasis on educating the public take root (Dunn, Jimmy, 2019).

Sustainable Architectural Designs for Museums

The design of museums has evolved throughout history. However, museum planning involves planning the actual mission of the museum along with planning the space that the collection of the museum will be housed in. Intentional museum planning has its beginnings with the museum founder and librarian John Cotton Dana. Dana detailed the process of founding the Newark Museum in a series of books in the early 20th century so that other museum founders could plan their museums. Dana suggested that potential founders of museums should form a committee first, and reach out to the community for input as to what the museum should supply or do for the community (Dana, 1917). According to Dana, museums should be planned according to community's needs: "The new museum ... does not build on an educational superstition. It examines its community's life first, and then straightway bends its energies to supplying some the material which that community needs, and to making that material's presence widely known, and to presenting it in such a way as to secure it for the maximum of use and the maximum efficiency of that use" (Dana, 1917).

Factors that influence the architectural design of cultural buildings

The specific location of a cultural building profoundly shapes its design. Architects must consider the surrounding topography, climate, existing infrastructure, and the immediate urban or natural environment. Buildings must respond to these elements, ensuring harmony with the landscape or providing intentional contrast. Sensitivity to the environment also encompasses sustainable design principles, promoting the use of locally sourced materials, energy efficiency, and the integration of natural elements like light and ventilation (Cole, 2012). Cultural buildings often serve as repositories of historical memory, community values, and artistic expression. Architects must delve into the intangible aspects of culture to inform their design choices. This includes understanding local traditions, symbolism, preferred materials, and the intended role of the building in the community. Cultural sensitivity ensures that the building resonates with the people it serves and reflects their unique identity (Markus, 1993).

Methodology

This study employed a descriptive research design to explore the feasibility and conceptualization of a sustainable museum. The target population includes the community, comprising residents, local organizations, and potential museum users. A purposive sampling technique was used to select a representative sample of stakeholders, including community leaders, educators, cultural practitioners, and environmental enthusiasts. Semi-structured interviews were used to collect data. To ensure validity and reliability, it was piloted with a small group, and questions were refined for clarity and comprehensiveness.

Perceptions of Preservation Challenges in Nigerian Museums

Table 1: Nigerian museums face significant challenges in preserving cultural artefacts and heritage.

Responses	Frequency	Frequency Percentage
Strongly Agree	20	40%
Agree	15	30%

Neutral	5	10%
Disagree	7	14%
Strongly Disagree	3	6%
Total	50	100%

The results in Table 1 show that a significant majority of respondents (70%) either strongly agree or agree that Nigerian museums face significant challenges in preserving cultural artifacts and heritage. This indicates a widespread recognition of the issue among the survey participants.

Table 2: Lack of adequate funding hampers preservation efforts in Nigerian museums.

Responses	Frequency	Frequency Percentage
Strongly Agree	25	50%
Agree	13	26%
Neutral	4	8%
Disagree	5	10%
Strongly Disagree	3	6%
Total	50	100%

Table 2 highlights that a majority (76%) believe that inadequate funding is a significant barrier to effective preservation in Nigerian museums. This suggests that financial constraints are a critical issue that needs addressing.

Table 3: Insufficient training and expertise among museum staff contribute to preservation challenges.

Responses	Frequency	Frequency Percentage
Strongly Agree	18	36%
Agree	17	34%
Neutral	7	14%
Disagree	5	10%
Strongly Disagree	3	6%
Total	50	100%

The data in Table 3 shows that 70% of respondents agree that insufficient training and expertise among museum staff contribute to preservation challenges, emphasizing the need for better training programs and capacity building.

Table 4: Inadequate infrastructure and technology hinder the preservation of cultural artifacts in Nigerian museums.

Responses	Frequency	Frequency Percentage
Strongly Agree	22	44%
Agree	15	30%
Neutral	5	10%
Disagree	5	10%
Strongly Disagree	3	6%

Total	50	100%
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Table 4 reveals that 74% of respondents believe that inadequate infrastructure and technology are major impediments to the preservation of cultural artifacts in Nigerian museums. This underscores the need for technological and infrastructural improvements.

Strategies for Safeguarding Cultural Heritage

Table 5: Implementing stricter regulations and policies for the protection of cultural artifacts.

Responses	Frequency	Frequency Percentage
Strongly Agree	23	46%
Agree	17	34%
Neutral	5	10%
Disagree	3	6%
Strongly Disagree	2	4%
Total	50	100%

As shown in Table 5, 80% of respondents support implementing stricter regulations and policies to protect cultural artifacts, indicating strong approval for more robust legal frameworks.

Table 6: Increasing public awareness and involvement in the preservation of cultural heritage.

Responses	Frequency	Frequency Percentage
Strongly Agree	20	40%
Agree	18	36%
Neutral	7	14%

Disagree	3	6%
Strongly Disagree	2	4%
Total	50	100%

Table 6 demonstrates that 76% of participants believe that increasing public awareness and involvement is crucial for cultural heritage preservation, highlighting the importance of community engagement.

Table 7: Collaborating with international organizations and experts to enhance preservation efforts.

Responses	Frequency	Frequency Percentage
Strongly Agree	21	42%
Agree	15	30%
Neutral	8	16%
Disagree	4	8%
Strongly Disagree	2	4%
Total	50	100%

Table 7 indicates that 72% support collaboration with international organizations and experts, suggesting that global partnerships are viewed as beneficial for enhancing preservation efforts.

Table 8: Investing in advanced preservation technologies and infrastructure.

Responses	Frequency	Frequency Percentage
Strongly Agree	25	50%
Agree	14	28%

Neutral	5	10%
Disagree	4	8%
Strongly Disagree	2	4%
Total	50	100%

Table 8 shows that 78% of respondents agree on the necessity of investing in advanced preservation technologies and infrastructure, underscoring the importance of technological advancements.

Suggestions for Improvement

Table 9: Increased funding allocation by the government for preservation initiatives.

Responses	Frequency	Frequency Percentage
Strongly Agree	26	52%
Agree	15	30%
Neutral	4	8%
Disagree	3	6%
Strongly Disagree	2	4%
Total	50	100%

As indicated in Table 9, a substantial majority (82%) strongly agree or agree that increasing government funding is critical for preservation initiatives, highlighting the need for greater financial support.

Table 10: Enhanced collaboration between Nigerian museums and international organizations for knowledge exchange and resource sharing.

Responses	Frequency	Frequency Percentage
Strongly Agree	24	48%

Agree	16	32%
Neutral	5	10%
Disagree	3	6%
Strongly Disagree	2	4%
Total	50	100%

Table 10 highlights that 80% of respondents favor enhanced collaboration between Nigerian museums and international organizations, suggesting this is a key strategy for improvement.

Table 11: Implementation of educational programs to raise public awareness about the significance of cultural heritage preservation.

Responses	Frequency	Frequency Percentage
Strongly Agree	22	44%
Agree	17	34%
Neutral	6	12%
Disagree	3	6%
Strongly Disagree	2	4%
Total	50	100%

The data in Table 11 reveals that 78% of participants support the implementation of educational programs to raise awareness, emphasizing the need for public education on cultural heritage.

Table 12: Adoption of modern conservation techniques and technologies in Nigerian museums.

Responses	Frequency	Frequency Percentage
Strongly Agree	23	46%
Agree	16	32%
Neutral	5	10%
Disagree	4	8%
Strongly Disagree	2	4%
Total	50	100%

Table 12 shows that 78% of respondents agree that adopting modern conservation techniques and technologies is necessary, pointing to the importance of innovation in preservation practices.

Discussion of findings

Key findings for the study include:

- Utilizing natural lighting and ventilation strategies will reduce dependence on artificial lighting and air conditioning.
- Integrating recycled and locally sourced materials in construction and exhibits will balance sustainability and functionality.
- Designing flexible spaces that can accommodate diverse community activities will provide a platform for community gatherings, fostering a sense of belonging and shared identity.
- Developing interactive cultural exhibits and programs will promote social interaction and cultural awareness.

Conclusion and recommendations

This study aimed to conceptualize and develop a plan for a sustainable museum that serves as both a functional center for community activities and a model for environmental responsibility. The proposed plan incorporates sustainable design principles to minimize environmental impact while promoting social cohesion through its focus on community engagement. The museum's flexible spaces and interactive programs can create a welcoming environment that promotes cultural exchange and strengthens the community fabric. This project demonstrates the potential for museums to contribute to a more sustainable and socially connected future.

The following recommendation were highlighted

- There is need to conduct community consultations and workshops to refine the design based on local needs and preferences.
- There is need to develop a detailed construction plan with cost estimates and identify potential funding sources.
- It is crucial to establish a team with expertise in sustainable design, museum management, and community engagement to oversee the project's implementation.
- Exploring best practices for promoting community engagement in museums is essential.
- It is necessary to develop metrics to evaluate the museum's social and environmental impact.

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